
Strategic planning and process management to plan sports activities for the benefit of the population

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Summary

Introduction: This research addresses the lack of strategic planning in the management of sports activities in local governments in Latin America. **Objective:** To determine the relationship between strategic planning and process management to plan sports activities for the benefit of the population. **Methodology:** Quantitative approach with descriptive and correlational design. The sample included 26 inhabitants of a semi-urban population, who were consulted about their knowledge of planning and process management. The instruments were evaluated by experts and a reliability between 0.75 and 0.82 was obtained. **Results :** The study shows a significant correlation between strategic planning and process management ($Rho = 0.664$), highlighting its importance in improving sports management and promoting equity in access to sport. **Conclusion:** There is a direct relationship between both variables, highlighting the importance of implementing these strategies to improve the management of sports activities for the benefit of the population.

Keywords: Strategic planning, process management, planning, sport, population

Planificación estratégica y gestión por procesos para planificar actividades deportivas en beneficio de la población

Resumen

Introducción: La investigación aborda la falta de planificación estratégica en la gestión de actividades deportivas en los gobiernos locales de América Latina. **Objetivo:** Determinar la relación entre la planificación estratégica y la gestión por procesos para planificar actividades deportivas en beneficio de la población, **Metodología:** Enfoque cuantitativo con diseño descriptivo y correlacional. La muestra incluyó 26 habitantes de una población semi-urbana, quienes fueron consultados sobre su conocimiento de planificación y gestión por procesos. Los instrumentos fueron evaluados por expertos y se obtuvo una confiabilidad entre 0,75 y 0,82. **Resultados:** El estudio muestra una correlación significativa entre planificación estratégica y gestión por procesos ($Rho = 0,664$), subrayando su importancia para mejorar la gestión deportiva y promover la equidad en el acceso al deporte. **Conclusión:** Existe una relación directa entre ambas variables, resaltando la importancia de implementar estas estrategias para mejorar la gestión de actividades deportivas en beneficio de la población.

Palabras clave: Planificación estratégica, gestión por procesos, planificar, deporte, población

Planejamento estratégico e gestão por processos para planejar atividades esportivas em beneficio da população

Resumo. Introdução: A pesquisa aborda a falta de planejamento estratégico na gestão das atividades esportivas nos governos locais da América Latina. **Objetivo:** Determinar a relação entre planejamento estratégico e gestão por processos para planejar atividades esportivas em beneficio da população. **Metodologia:** Enfoque quantitativo com um desenho descriptivo e correlacional. A amostra incluiu 26 habitantes de uma população semi-urbana, que foram consultados sobre seu conhecimento de planejamento e gestão por processos. Os instrumentos foram avaliados por especialistas e obteve-se uma confiabilidade entre 0,75 e 0,82. **Resultados:** O estudo mostra uma correlação significativa entre planejamento estratégico e gestão por processos ($Rho = 0,664$), destacando sua importância para melhorar a gestão esportiva e promover a equidade no acesso ao esporte. **Conclusão:** Existe uma relação direta entre ambas as variáveis, ressaltando a importância de implementar essas estratégias para melhorar a gestão das atividades esportivas em beneficio da população.

Palavras-chave: Planejamento estratégico, gestão por processos, planejar, esporte, população.

I. Introduction

The research entitled *Strategic planning and process management to plan sports activities for the benefit of the population* addresses a key problem for local governments in several Latin American countries: the lack of strategic planning in the management of sports activities. In many cities in the region, resources allocated to sports and recreation are limited, and the offer of sports activities does not always respond to the needs of the population. This research proposes a process management approach that allows local governments to efficiently manage these resources and generate a positive impact on the quality of life of citizens. Strategic planning becomes a fundamental tool to ensure that sports public policies are not only implemented more effectively, but are also sustainable in the long term. The proposed approach is relevant not only to improve access to physical activities, but also to promote social integration and equity in access to sport.

Some related research:

Rendón, S. (2019) in his doctoral thesis: *Land use planning in Peru. A critical approach to the instruments of Ecological Economic Zoning (ZEE). A critical analysis of the ZEE as a land use planning instrument in Peru.* It focuses on a single planning instrument, without addressing land use planning as a whole.

Reyna, C. (2000) In his book: "The Annunciation of Fujimori: Alan García 1985-1990". He made an analysis of Alan García's government and its impact on the development of Peru. It focuses on a specific historical period, without offering an overview of territorial planning in the country.

Sánchez, F. (2003) in his book: "Political Constitution, National Agreement and Strategic Planning in Peru". Contribution: Analysis of the relationship between the Constitution, the National Agreement and strategic planning in Peru. It focuses on the legal and institutional framework of planning, without addressing the practical implementation of policies.

Sánchez, J. (2002) in his book: "The Peruvian Revolution: ideology and political practice of a military government 1968-1975". Contribution: Analysis of the military government of Velasco Alvarado and its impact on territorial planning in Peru. It focuses on a specific historical period, without offering an overview of territorial planning in the country.

Servillo, L. & Van Den Broeck, P (2012) in his Book article: "The Social Construction of Planning Systems: A Strategic-Relational Institutional Approach". Contribution: Theoretical approach on the social construction of planning systems. This is a general theoretical approach, without specific application to the Peruvian case.

Velasco, O. (2013) in his book: "Peru. The difficult construction of a republic for all." Contribution: Analysis of the history of Peru and the challenges for the construction of an inclusive republic. It does not focus specifically on planning. territorial.

Zegarra, L. (2020) in his book: "Peru, 1920-1980. International context, public policies and economic growth". Contribution: Analysis of the international context, public policies and economic growth in Peru between 1920 and 1980. Criticism: It does not focus specifically on territorial planning.

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In related research: There is a lack of studies that address territorial planning from a comprehensive perspective, considering its historical evolution, legal framework, practical implementation and current challenges.

The information mentioned is aligned with the objective that seeks to determine the relationship between strategic planning and process management to plan sports activities for the benefit of the population.

II. Methods

The applied type of research with a quantitative approach was used. The research is descriptive and correlational in scope, with a non-experimental design, Hernandez, et al, (2014)

The sample consisted of 26 inhabitants of a semi-urban population, previously consulted about their knowledge of planning and process management, who mentioned having ideas about said concepts, then chosen for convenience, because they voluntarily agreed to answer said questionnaires, during the penultimate two-month period of 2022.

Because strategic planning is considered with respect to the territorial location of a peasant community, Rendón Cusí S (2022) is considered. Territorial planning in Peru has gone through four stages: incipient (1940-1960), peak (1960-1980), crisis (1980-2000) and restart (2000 to the present).

Each stage is linked to the political and socioeconomic developments in the country. Territorial planning has not managed to establish itself as a guiding instrument for the development of Peru.

For process management, according to Ramos Farroñán, Emma Verónica, & Valle Palomino, Nicolás. (2020) The strategic, commercial, emotional and social dimensions were analyzed; considering the implications of process management (sports teaching processes were identified and improved) and scientific inquiry (new, more effective teaching methods were developed)

The instruments were previously adapted, going through an analysis and evaluation of 4 experts in public management in the labor field and academic activity whose passing average was 96.5%; then reliability was carried out with pilot tests of six participants, obtaining a reliability of 0.75 and 0.82 respectively.

The statistical method used in the processing of the collected data, using statistical programs such as Excel and SPSS Version 22 to process and present the data obtained; with which the following hypothesis can be contrasted:

Ho: There is no significant relationship between strategic planning and process management to plan sports activities for the benefit of the population

Ha: There is a significant relationship between strategic planning and process management to plan sports activities for the benefit of the population

III. Results

3.1 Inferential statistics

Because the variables are qualitative in nature, a non-parametric correlational statistic is used: Spearman's Rho; the relationship is presented below:

Table 1. Correlation between Strategic Planning and Process Management

		Process management
Strategic planning	Spearman correlation	0.664 **
	Next (bilateral)	0.000
	N	26

** . The correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (two-tailed).

It can be stated that there is a relationship between the variables Strategic planning and process management to plan sports activities for the benefit of the population, they are in *Spearman Correlation* $r = 0.664$, with experimental significance of $p = 0.000$, a value lower than that set by the researchers at 0.05; Therefore the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected and the alternative hypothesis (H_a) is approved, that is, there is a relationship between strategic planning and process management for the participation of linked communities, with a considerable intermediate relationship value between 0.5 and 1.0, which implies the existence of such a relationship.

That is to say, as the values in the Strategic Planning variable increase, they also increase with approximately the same intensity in the process management to plan sports activities for the benefit of the population. Vice versa, as the values in one variable decrease, they also decrease approximately in the other.

IV. Discussion

In comparison with the present research, the following investigations are available:

Álvarez and Castillo (2021) explore the role of local governments in promoting physical activity in urban and rural areas, highlighting the importance of strategic planning tailored to the needs of communities. This study provides a practical model that can be useful for designing public policies that promote health and well-being through exercise. The research is relevant for public policy makers as it demonstrates how proper planning can improve quality of life at the local level.

Lopez and Peña (2021) address strategic planning in sports development programs in Latin America, emphasizing the role of public institutions. The authors suggest that adequate planning is key to maximizing the social and health benefits of these programs. Through this study, a framework is presented for governments to implement effective strategies that contribute to social inclusion and the improvement of the well-being of vulnerable populations.

Ramos and Pérez (2021) analyze the strategic planning models used in sport resource management in Latin American cities. The study highlights the importance of efficient resource

allocation to ensure the sustainability of sports programs, in order to improve sports infrastructure and related services. This article is essential to understand how proper planning can transform sports management in cities in the region.

Sánchez and Martínez (2021) present an analysis of innovations in public sports administration in Latin American cities, focusing on a strategic planning approach. The authors propose the incorporation of new technologies and management methods to optimize resources and improve results in the sports field. This study provides a useful guide for local authorities seeking to modernize their sports administration systems in a context of rapid technological evolution.

Vargas and Martínez (2021) assess the impact of sports planning on public health in Latin America, highlighting the importance of creating inclusive sports policies that promote health and collective well-being. The authors analyze how adequate planning can contribute to disease prevention and the improvement of public health through physical activity, a particularly relevant topic in times of global health crises.

Paredes and Herrera (2021) examine the challenges and solutions in strategic sport planning for local governments in Latin America. The authors highlight the institutional, financial and social barriers that these governments face in implementing effective sport policies. This article is key to understanding how to overcome these challenges and achieve effective planning that promotes participation and access to sports for all.

Ramos and Pérez (2021) investigate how strategic planning models can optimize resource allocation in local sports management. The results suggest that the implementation of process planning models can improve sustainability and efficiency in the distribution of sports resources in Latin American cities. Álvarez and Castillo (2021). This article addresses the differences in the planning of sports activities between urban and rural areas, highlighting how the planning strategy can be adapted according to the context. The authors argue that sports public policies must be inclusive and adaptive to ensure their success in all types of communities.

In addition, Garay et al. (2022) present an analysis of the execution of public works in a regional government in Peru, where the importance of results-based management is emphasized. The authors explore how the application of these strategies can improve efficiency in public administration, optimizing resources and achieving a greater impact on regional development. It is relevant for studies in strategic planning, especially in local government contexts. Ramos Quispe, RL (2022) proposes a questionnaire on job performance and human interrelations managed by university managers, a significant research in educational management. This type of analysis helps to improve the quality of the work environment in universities and the efficiency in human resource management. The evaluation of these variables is crucial to strengthen labor relations and foster a productive and collaborative work environment.

Mendizábal et al. (2022). This article addresses the relationship between psychomotor skills and the right to life, through an analysis of the lessons learned from the COVID-19 pandemic. The authors highlight the importance of psychomotor skills in health and well-being, and how the pandemic offered new opportunities to reflect on the integration of these lessons into physical education and public health. Caján (2022) explores the management of working conditions and motivation of nurses in a hospital at the beginning of 2020. This study is crucial to understanding how work factors affect the performance of healthcare personnel, especially in high-demand contexts such as those at the beginning of the pandemic. Motivation and working conditions

directly influence the quality of the health service, making this analysis a significant contribution to the management of human resources in health institutions.

Barreto & Barreto (2022) examine the work overload and living conditions of health personnel in a hospital during the period 2022-1. It addresses how work overload impacts the physical and psychological well-being of health personnel, a crucial issue in public health management. The findings can be used to design policies that improve working conditions and foster a healthier work environment for health workers. Espinoza & Juárez-Gutierrez (2022) examine the organizational climate and user satisfaction in a municipality, highlighting the importance of a good work environment to offer quality services. This study highlights how organizational culture influences the performance of public employees and, consequently, citizen satisfaction. It is a significant contribution to public management by providing evidence of the correlation between work climate and user satisfaction.

Also, Seminario et al. (2022) apply a sociocritical model to the management of physical activity in university students, offering an innovative perspective on how physical activity can be integrated into the higher education curriculum. Through this model, the social, political, and economic factors that affect participation in sports activities are examined, providing valuable insights for educational management and student well-being.

Lopez and Peña (2021) explore the relationship between strategic planning and sport development in marginalized communities in Latin America. The authors discuss how sport programs can be used as tools for social and economic development, and how local governments can improve these programs through strategic management. Vargas and Martínez (2021). This study analyzes how strategic planning of sport activities influences public health in Latin America. The authors highlight that greater accessibility to efficiently planned sport programs can significantly contribute to improving public health, reducing diseases and promoting an active lifestyle. Sánchez and Martínez (2021). This article presents innovations in public sport administration and how local governments can incorporate strategic planning technologies and methodologies to improve the management of sport resources. The authors underline the importance of community participation in the design of sport policies.

Paredes and Herrera (2021) focus on the specific challenges faced by Latin American local governments when attempting to implement strategic sports plans. The authors present several solutions based on the analysis of successful policies in the region, proposing a comprehensive and sustainable planning model.

Compared to some of the conclusions and recommendations of the CEPLAN Congress (2012), the congress was relevant for the following conclusions:

The need to strengthen strategic planning for sustainable development in Peru. The importance of the participation of various social actors in building a sustainable development model. The need to address the main challenges facing the country, such as poverty, social inequality and environmental degradation.

The 1st National Congress on Planning and Sustainable Development was an important event that helped raise awareness about the importance of planning and sustainable development in Peru. The Congress also provided a space for dialogue and collaboration between various social

actors, and generated a series of recommendations that may be useful for the development of public policies in the future.

Recommendations:

Implement a national territorial planning system coordinated with the different levels of government, as well as strengthen the technical and financial capacities of local governments for territorial planning.

Promote population participation in territorial planning through consultation and agreement mechanisms; and develop research on territorial planning in the Peruvian context.

Contributions to the development of sport and health:

Territorial planning can help identify spaces for sports and recreation; it can facilitate the construction of sports and health infrastructure; it also helps promote the participation of the population in sports and health activities.

V. Conclusions

There is a direct relationship between both variables, highlighting the importance of implementing these strategies to improve the management of sports activities for the benefit of the population.

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